

Electron microscopy study and vulcanization characteristics of insoluble sulfur

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Usage of insoluble sulfur in rubber industry, particularly in pneumatic automotive tyre, is an well established fact. It's advantages e.g. avoiding blooming on surface and retention of tack etc. are well known and recognized. In case of a powdered material particle size and shape are the two basic parameters to be considered for incorporation, distribution and dispersion in rubber compound. Dispersion of insoluble sulfur in rubber compound is critical because of its small particle size and tendency to agglomerate due to electrostatic charge which can result in non homogeneous compound (vulcanizate) properties.

Studies carried out (SEM and TEM, Rheometry and physico-mechanical properties of vulcanizates) show that insoluble sulfur from different sources do not have any noticeable effect on the dispersion aspect and vulcanization characteristics as well as vulcanizate properties of rubber compounds studied here.

Usage of insoluble sulfur in rubber industry, particularly in pneumatic automotive tyre, is an well established fact. It's advantages e.g. avoiding blooming on surface and retention of tack etc. are well known and recognized.

Insoluble sulfur is polymeric sulfur and is insoluble in elastomers. Consequently it retards scorching of compound, prevent migration of sulfur and preserve surface tack. This is important in the manufacture of pneumatic tyre for retention of tack of carcass (plies of calendared fabric) and belt compound, other built-up rubber articles like hose, belting, coated fabric etc. and retraining material. At vulcanization temperatures insoluble sulfur depolymerizes to soluble sulfur and behave similar to normal sulfur¹.

Insoluble sulfur is produced by different process by different manufacturer suited best to them with respect to quality, cost and energy consumption. In case of a powdered material particle size and shape are the two basic parameters to be considered for incorporation, distribution and dispersion in rubber compound. Dispersion of insoluble sulfur in rubber compound is critical because of its small particle size and tendency to agglomerate due to electrostatic charge which can result in non homogeneous compound (vulcanizate) properties.

As insoluble sulfur is insoluble in rubber, higher level can be used in compound without loosing green compound tack which is not possible with normal sulfur as it would lead to sulfur bloom. However, sometimes it is difficult to disperse insoluble sulfur in rubber compound. Due to this different types of insoluble sulfur have been developed with

additives which leads to improved dispersion.

One international pneumatic tyre manufacturer² have reported about varied particle shape and size of insoluble sulfur from different manufacturer and expressed apprehension about irregular particle shape effect on the belt edge of the radial tyre in private discussion.

With this background studies were carried out with samples of insoluble sulfur from different manufacturer and grades which were analysed for their particle shape and size with the help of Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) as well as whether these have any effect on vulcanization characteristics and vulcanizate properties of typical rubber compounds (ASTM and belt compound).

Results and discussion

Electron microscopy :

Particle size and shape study was carried out by Transmission Electron Microscopy as explained above. Pictures of these micrographs for different samples at magnifications (155000X) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

It can be seen that the samples contain particles having polyhedral and circular shapes. The particles of insoluble sulfur with 20% oil coating (Sample No. I) found to be polyhedral in shape and the size vary from 6 nm to 10 nm. Whereas the particles of similar insoluble sulfur from another manufacturing source (Sample No. II) found to be circular in shape and their size vary from 6 nm to 90 nm. These observations indicate that the insoluble sulfur avail-

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

able commercially in the market have broad range of particle size though all of them are polyhedral/circular in shape. Surface morphology study of the samples was carried out using Scanning Electron Microscopy as explained above (Figs. 3 and 4).

Scanning Electron Microscopy of chemically treated insoluble sulfur samples shows spherulitic agglomerates. The shape of the particles is spherular and size of these particles is varying from 270 nm to 800 nm. However majority of the spherular particles are in the range of 350 nm (Figs. 3a and 3b). Sample of insoluble sulfur from another manufacturing source also shows similar surface morphology where the size is varying from 400 nm to 1 μm , with majority of particle in the range of 500 nm to 700 nm (Fig. 4).

The sample of such chemically treated insoluble sulfur as analyzed above contain particles having polyhedral and spherule shape. Some scattered rod like particles have also been observed. The size of the polyhedral particles were found to vary from 75 nm to 550 nm and the size of spherular particles is varying from 75 nm to 175 nm.

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 4

Vulcanization characteristics of compound : Curing characteristics of compound containing different insoluble sulfur was studied as per ASTM D 5289³ with Rheometer (MDR 2000) keeping all factors constant. Rheometry results are presented in Table 1. It can be seen that the results of rheometry are closely comparable with both insoluble sulfur samples evaluated here.

Table 1. Rheometric data of compounds

Sample No.	I	II	III	IV
Initial Viscosity Lo (in lb)	–	–	–	–
Mini. Viscosity Li (in lb)	2.60	2.60	2.20	2.30
Thermoplasticity	–	–	–	–
Tp (Lo-Li) (in lb)				
Induction time – time for one units rise above Li (min)	2.15	2.32	2.35	2.30
Scorch time-t ₁₂ – time for two units rise above Li (min)	2.65	2.87	2.90	2.75
Max. cure-Lf (in lb)	33.50	33.20	33.80	32.70
Max. cure time – t ₁₀₀				
Optimum cure – 0.9 (Lf-Li) + Li (in lb)	30.41	30.14	30.64	29.66
Optimum cure time – t ₉₀ (min)	13	14	12	12

The physico-mechanical properties of the vulcanizate are given in Table 2 which shows closely comparable values in both the cases.

Further Rheometric studies were carried out with a typical passenger radial belt skim compound at three different temperatures (130°, 140° and 150°C) with two insoluble sul-

Table 2. Physical properties of vulcanizates

Sample description	I	II	III	IV
Optimum cure time (min) t ₉₀ at 150°C	13	14	12	12
100% Modulus (MPa)	11	11	12	12
200% Modulus (MPa)	20	21	21	22
300% Modulus (MPa)	38	40	42	40
Tensile strength (MPa)	121	135	125	141
Elongation at break (%)	570	600	580	600
Hardness (Shore-A)	47	46	47	55

fur samples and energy of activation of these compounds were calculated. These are presented in Tables 3 and 4 and Fig. 6.

It can be seen in this case also Rheometric parameters of both samples are closely comparable in all respect. Energy of activation was calculated by Arrhenius equation

$$k = Ae^{-E/RT}$$

where *k* is rate constant, *A* is a constant, *E* is activation energy and *R* – gas constant and *T* is absolute temperature. Activation energy of both samples from two manufacturing sources are very close indicating no effect on the vulcanization characteristics of the compound.

Table 3. Rheometric study (ASTM D 5289 . MDR 2000)

Sample details	Min. TQ (lb-inch)	Max. TQ (lb-inch)	Ts1 (min)	Ts2 (min)	Tc40 (min)	Tc50 (min)	Tc90 (min)
Time 120 min; Temp. 130°C							
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 1	2.66	19.75	14.51	17.46	26.81	30.32	62.59
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 2	2.76	20.68	13.18	15.96	25.13	28.54	60.95
Time 120 min; Temp. 140°C							
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 1	2.44	18.93	6.59	8.19	12.58	14.23	30.01
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 2	2.40	19.50	6.02	7.51	11.96	13.61	29.29
Time 120 min; Temp. 150°C							
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 1	2.19	17.76	3.08	3.94	6.10	6.92	14.18
Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound–Sample 2	2.33	18.61	2.29	3.69	5.84	6.65	14.03

Table 4. Activation energy study

Sl. no.	Sample details	Activation energy (kcal/mol)
1.	Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim Compound-Sample 1	20.18
2.	Standard Passenger Radial belt Skim compound-Sample 2	20.21

Activation energy calculation for : INSOLUBLE S 1

Sl. no.	K (lb-in/min)	T (°K)	ln K	1/T	E (kcal/mol)
1.	0.7	403	-0.36	2.481×10^{-3}	
2.	1.2	413	0.18	2.421×10^{-3}	20.21
3.	2.3	423	0.83	2.364×10^{-3}	

From graph 1 : Slope = $-E/R = -10.157$

Gas constant $R = 1.987$

Kelvin = Deg centigrade + 273

Rate of reaction (K) is from rheograph under heading peak rate.

Activation energy calculation for : INSOLUBLE S 2

Sl. no.	K (lb-in/min)	T (°K)	ln K	1/T	E (kcal/mol)
1.	0.7	403	-0.36	2.481×10^{-3}	
2.	1.2	413	0.18	2.421×10^{-3}	20.21
3.	2.3	423	0.83	2.364×10^{-3}	

From graph 2 : Slope = $-E/R = -10.169$

Gas constant $R = 1.987$

Kelvin = Deg centigrade + 273

Rate of reaction (K) is from rheograph under heading peak rate.

Fig. 5

Standard Passenger Radial Tyre Belt Wire Skim Compound

Fig. 6. Activation energy of insoluble sulfur.

Coating of insoluble sulfur :

Insoluble sulfur are marketed mostly in coated form – oil or chemical treated to reduce dust formation during handling and mixing thus minimizing loss and improvement in dispersion compared to non-coated material. Usage of special additives to enhance dispersion and faster incorporation of insoluble sulfur is now commercially available.

Attempt was made to identify such chemical additive groups which result in better dispersion and faster incorporation. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS) analysis was carried out with the extract of special grade of insoluble sulfur to identify such chemical groups (Figs. 7(a)-(d)). Chromatographic picture of such GC-MS analysis is quite complex and simple conclusion cannot be drawn.

IPMRA - THANE

<Unknown Spectrum>
 Data : INSO.D03
 Mass Peak # : 53 Ret. Time : 10.075
 Scan # : 1150
 Base Peak : 55.05 (244961)

<Hit List>

No	SI	Mol. Wgt.	Mol. Form /Compound Name	CAS No.	Entry	LIB#
1	91	254	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, n-tridecyl ester \$\$	- -0	56330	1
2	90	282	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, n-pentadecyl ester \$\$	- -0	66033	1
3	89	240	C ₁₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ Dodecyl acrylate ✓	2156-97-0	15312	2
4	89	240	C ₁₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ Dodecyl acrylate \$\$ n-Lauryl acrylate \$\$ 2-Propenoic acid, dodecyl ester \$\$ n-Dodecyl acrylate \$\$ Acrylic acid, dodecyl ester \$\$ Lauryl acrylate \$\$	2156-97-0	51265	1
5	89	196	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ 5-Tetradecene, (E) - \$\$	41446-66-6	33144	1

Library Name

(1) NIST107.LIB (2) NIST21.LIB (3) WILEY139.LIB

Fig. 7(a) and (b)

However, the analysis and library search indicate presence of compounds (additive groups) like dodecyl ester or n-docyl methacrylate, dodecane, 2-methyl-8-propyl and dodecyl acrylate in different samples tested. Further studies are needed to arrive at a meaningful conclusion.

Experimental

Samples of insoluble sulfur :

Different samples of insoluble sulfur from different

sources as listed below (Table 5) were used for SEM/TEM and Rheometry study. For study of dispersion of insoluble sulfur in rubber, oil coated samples of 20% oil content and special grades of polymer/chemical coated insoluble sulfur were chosen for the study. Typical analysis values of insoluble sulfur is also given therein. Electron Microscopy were carried out with selected samples.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)-Jeol (Jem) 200 CX :

<Unknown Spectrum>
 Data : INSOHD.D00
 Mass Peak # : 132 Ret. Time : 10.675
 Scan # : 1222
 Base Peak : 41.00 (1155173)

<Hit List>

No	SI	Mol. Wgt.	Mol. Form. /Compound Name	CAS No.	Entry	LIB#
1	95	254	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, dodecyl ester	142-90-5	15970	2
2	91	254	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, dodecyl ester \$\$ Methacrylic acid, dodecyl ester \$\$ Acrylic acid, 2-methyl-, dodecyl ester \$\$ Dodecyl methacrylate \$\$ Dodecyl 2-methyl- 1-2-propenoate \$\$ Lauryl methacrylate \$\$ Metazene \$\$ Methacrylic acid, lauryl est er \$\$ 1-Dodecanol methacrylate \$\$ Laurylester kyseliny methakrylove \$\$ Ageflex fm 246 \$\$ Dodecyl ester of 2-methyl-2-propenoic acid \$\$	142-90-5	56341	1
3	91	226	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, decyl ester \$\$ n-Decyl methacrylate \$\$ Methacrylic a cid, decyl ester \$\$ Decyl methacrylate \$\$	3179-47-3	45937	1
4	91	226	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ 2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, decyl ester \$\$ n-Decyl methacrylate \$\$ Methacrylic a cid, decyl ester \$\$	3179-47-3	61996	3
5	87	254	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂ Cyclopropanecarboxylic acid, dodecyl ester \$\$	- -0	56332	1

Library Name
 (1) NIST107.LIB (2) NIST21.LIB (3) WILEY139.LIB

Fig. 7 (c) and (d)

Procedure for specimen preparation : The specimen for electron microscopic examination were prepared by dispersing a small quantity of powder in dimethyl formamide (DMF) in a test tube. After shaking the suspension in an ultrasonic bath, the dispersed sample was taken from the

middle of the test tube and droplets were spread on the specimen grids covered with plastic (formvar) film. After drying, the grids were transferred into the electron microscope for examination. Different regions of specimen grids were scanned carefully and pictures were recorded at suitable

Table 5.

(a) Insoluble sulfur samples	
Sample no.	Insoluble sulfur type
I	OT-20 - Manufacturer A
II	OT-20 - Manufacturer B
III	OT-20 - Manufacturer B, Polymer coated
IV	OT-20 - Manufacturer A, Chemical coated
(b) Typical values of insoluble sulfur	
Appearance	Yellow powder
Insoluble sulfur (on total S) (%) min	90
Total sulfur content (%)	78.5–81.5
Ash (%) max	0.05
Total binder content (%) min	75
Acidity (as H ₂ SO ₄) (%) max	0.05
Typical properties	
Specific gravity at 20°C (kg/m ³)	1.61
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	350–550
Compacted bulk density (kg/m ³)	550–800
Mean particle size (µm)	<30
(c) Compound formulation for Rheometric study	
Chemicals	phr
ISNR-5	100
A/O 6 PPD	1
A/O TDQ	1
Stearic acid	2
Zinc oxide	5
Carbon black N-660 (GPF)	40
Aromatic oil	6
N-Oxiethylene benzothiazole 2-sulphenamide	0.65
Insoluble sulfur	2.25

areas and magnifications.

Surface structure using Scanning Electron Microscopy (Model Leo 440, Cambridge, UK).

Characterization details :

Surface structure : The specimen for surface structure studies using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) were prepared by sprinkling the powder by blowing on to the specimen stubs having conducting carbon tape and double sided adhesive tape mounted on them. Thereafter the specimen were given a coating of gold for making them conducting to electron beam. The samples thus prepared were transferred to electron microscope for carrying out the microscopy. The SEM of the samples were done at an accelerating voltage of 1–4 kV and at probe current of 60 pA. The samples were thoroughly scanned and pictures were recorded at suitable areas and magnification.

Vulcanization characteristics and vulcanizate properties :

Vulcanization characteristics of the compound made with samples of insoluble sulfur was carried out with Rheometer (MDR 2000) at 150°C. Compound formulation used for the study is given in Table 5(c).

Acknowledgement

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